

EHDEN

EUROPEAN HEALTH DATA & EVIDENCE NETWORK

806968 – EHDEN

European Health Data & Evidence Network

WP3 – Personalized Medicine

D3.1 Selection of Use Cases for Personalized Medicine

Lead contributor	Peter R. Rijnbeek (1 – EMC)
Lead contributor email	p.rijnbeek@erasmusmc.nl
Other contributors	1 – EMC 3 – UOXF 4 – UTARTU
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DOCUMENT HISTORY

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DEFINITIONS

Participants of the EHDEN Consortium are referred to herein according to the following codes:

EMC	Erasmus Universitair Medisch Centrum Rotterdam- The Netherlands (Project Coordinator)
Synapse	Synapse Research Management Partners S.L. - Spain
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford - United Kingdom
UTARTU	Tartu Ulikool - Estonia
UAVR	Universidade de Aveiro – Portugal
The Hyve	The Hyve BV – the Netherlands
Odysseus	Odysseus Data Services SRO – Czech Republic
EPF	Forum Europeen des Patients (FPE) - Luxembourg
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence – United Kingdom
UMC	Stiftelsen WHO Collaborating Centre for International Drug Monitoring - Sweden
ICHOM	International Consortium for Health Outcomes measurement LTD - United Kingdom
Janssen	Janssen Pharmaceutica NV - Belgium (Project Lead)
Pfizer	Pfizer Limited – United Kingdom
Abbvie	AbbVie Inc - United States
IRIS	Institut De Recherches Internationales Servier - France
SARD	Sanofi Aventis Recherche & Developpement - France
Bayer	Bayer Aktiengesellschaft - Germany
Lilly	Eli Lilly and Company Limited – United Kingdom
AZ	AstraZeneca AB - Sweden
Novartis	Novartis Pharma AG - Switzerland
UCB	UCB Biopharma SPRL - Belgium
Celgene	Celgene Management SARL - Switzerland

Grant agreement	The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the IMI JU for the undertaking of the EHDEN project (806968).
Project	The sum of all activities carried out in the framework of the Grant Agreement.
Consortium	The EHDEN Consortium, comprising the above-mentioned legal entities.
Consortium agreement	Agreement concluded amongst EHDEN participants for the implementation of the Grant Agreement. Such an agreement shall not affect the parties' obligations to the Community and/or to one another arising from the Grant Agreement.
OHDSI	Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (www.ohdsi.org)
OMOP-CDM	Common Data Model developed in the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership project.

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The Personalized Medicine Work Package (WP3) in the European Health Data and Evidence Network (EHDEN) project, aims to further develop the analytical pipelines for Patient-Level Prediction and Population-Level Effect Estimation from the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) initiative and will develop a pipeline for assessing Disease Trajectories. This first deliverable of WP3 describes a first selection of use cases in these three domains that will drive the development of the EHDEN infrastructure. This includes methodological research, but also developments for the dissemination of the results in the form of dashboard. Moreover, the use case will demonstrate the power of the data standardisation through the OMOP Common Data Model by executing studies in multiple clinical domains. WP3 has already been able to apply the pipelines in study-a-thons, has presented results in high-impact conferences, and has submitted several publications on these topics. This deliverable also briefly describes these results.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Utilising the large amount of health data for personalized decision-making has been hampered by the lack of inter-operability of the available data sources. The European Health Data and Evidence Network (EHDEN) project will standardise large amount of health data sources across Europe to the OMOP Common Data Model. This enables the development of analytical pipelines that could have a high impact on personalized medicine. WP3 will further develop Patient-Level Prediction, Population-Level Effect Estimation pipelines from the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) initiative and will develop a pipeline for Disease Trajectories.

Patient-Level Prediction aims to predict better which subgroups of patients are likely to develop a disease, which patients will switch to which treatment, which patients will adhere to treatment, etc. This may lead to better tailored products, solutions, or services for disease prevention. Patient-level predictive modelling could be applied to the prediction of side effects and could be part of new risk minimization strategies. Moreover, ascertainment of patient characteristics that result in a beneficial outcome of the treatment would also be of major value. EHDEN therefore aims to enable the development and evaluation of patient-level prediction models and risk effect estimation across Europe. This will include prediction models on a very large number of cohorts, for many outcomes.

Furthermore, WP3 will further develop and apply OHDSI's population-level risk effect estimation pipeline. This pipeline is used to estimate the average causal effects of exposures, e.g. medical interventions such as drug exposures or procedures. The method attempts to emulate a randomized clinical trial (1). Subjects that are observed to initiate one treatment (the target) are compared to subjects initiating another treatment (the comparator) and are followed for a specific amount of time following treatment initiation, for example the time they stay on the treatment.

Finally, the work package will develop a pipeline to assess how diseases develop over time, how diagnoses follow each other, and what are the main pathways from particular health-related event to another. This knowledge could be utilized for better disease prediction, prevention, etc.

In EHDEN WP1 "Evidence Workflow Development", WP2 "Outcome Driven Healthcare" and WP3 "Personalized Medicine" have been designed to drive the development of the EHDEN technical framework (WP4) and the processes involved in the data workflow (WP5). This will include the execution of studies in the EHDEN data network to demonstrate the value of the analytical pipelines.

In summary, WP3 has to following objectives:

1. To establish a standardized process to enable personalized decision-making that can be utilized for multiple outcomes of interest and can be applied to observational healthcare data from any patient subpopulation of interest available in the OMOP-CDM.
2. To further extend and integrate the OHDSI framework for the development of well-calibrated patient-centred predictive models.
3. To further extend and integrate the OHDSI framework for evidence generation using risk-effect estimation methods.
4. To develop a framework for large-scale assessment of disease trajectories using observational data stored in the OMOP-CDM.
5. To demonstrate the use of the EHDEN ecosystem for personalized medicine through high-impact use cases.
6. To train the community in utilizing the EHDEN infrastructure and methods related to patient-level prediction, risk effect estimation, and disease trajectories.

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To drive tool and process development, this deliverable describes a number of high-impact use cases for personalized decision-making that have been selected in close collaboration with WP1 and WP2, and our EHDEN stakeholders.

2. USE CASES

The use cases described in more detail below have been selected after face-to-face discussions with the EHDEN consortium members, multiple teleconferences, and feedback from experts in the personalized medicine domain. The selection is also driven by the active participation in workgroups in OHDSI of several of our consortium partners (EMC, UOXF, The Hyve etc). In the next sections we will briefly describe the use cases in WP3 that are currently prioritized. During the project lifetime additional use cases will be developed.

2.1 Predictive Analytics

Clinical decision making is a complicated task in which the clinician has to infer a diagnosis or treatment pathway based on the available medical history of the patient and the current clinical guidelines. Based on this assessment the clinician has to decide on a treatment plan together with the patient. Clinical prediction models have been developed to support this decision-making process and are used in clinical practice in a wide spectrum of specialties. These models predict a diagnostic or prognostic outcome based on a combination of patient characteristics, e.g. demographic information, disease history, or treatment history. Most currently used models are estimated using small datasets and contain a limited set of patient characteristics. This low sample size, and thus low statistical power, forces the data analyst to make stronger modelling assumptions. The selection of the often-limited set of patient characteristics is strongly guided by the expert knowledge at hand. This contrasts sharply with the reality of modern medicine wherein patients generate a rich digital trail, which is well beyond the power of any medical practitioner to fully assimilate. Currently, it is unknown how much predictive accuracy can be gained by utilising the large amount of data originating from all the available data in the EHR of a patient. Moreover, current prediction models often lack external validation, which limits their clinical applicability.

In EHDEN we will optimally utilize the ongoing developments in the OHDSI community in this area. EMC is leading the patient-level prediction workgroup in OHDSI together with JANSSEN and has already implemented a first version of a patient-level prediction framework that runs on top of the OMOP-CDM, which will be further developed and validated in EHDEN (2). This open source framework enables a fully standardised process to develop and evaluate clinical prediction models using a large set of machine learning methods. The framework enables external validation of the models at scale by fully utilising the standardized EHDEN data network. The methodological focus in the use cases in this domain will be on the addition of new machine learning methods and advanced feature engineering capabilities for prediction, for example temporal data analyses using deep learning, and distributed learning across the network. Furthermore, we will investigate and pilot the integration of novel data types such as unstructured textual data and determine how it can be used as a real-world data source for the development and evaluation of predictive algorithms. Finally, these use cases will be valuable for deliverable D3.3 that explores guidelines and regulations for predictive model development, evaluation, and adoption.

2.1.1 Prediction Study-a-thons

During the project lifetime we will develop and validate a large amount of prediction models. This will be driven by study-a-thons in which we will bring a group of experts together that have all the necessary expertise to design, implement, and validate the prediction models. Interestingly, we have already been able to perform multiple study-a-thons in the first 7 months of the EHDEN project that have resulted in valuable new prediction models for multiple domains.

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As an example, in project month 2 we performed a 5-day study-a-thon at Oxford University on the topic of Elective total knee replacement (TKR) which is a safe and cost-effective treatment for severe knee osteoarthritis (OA). Although complications following surgery are rare, prediction tools could help identify at risk subjects to target with preventative interventions. We there brought together 42 researchers, including clinical experts, data scientists. In this exciting week, we designed, implemented, and executed a multinational, multi-database cohort analysis using electronic medical records and claims data from the US and the UK. Seven data sources that were standardised to the OMOP-CDM were used. All subjects undergoing a first TKR, aged 40 years or older and registered in any of the contributing data sources for at least 1 year before surgery were included. Key adverse outcomes included post-operative (90-day) mortality, venous thrombo-embolism, infection, readmission; and long-term (5-year) revision surgery. Lasso logistic regression models were fit independently in 5 data sources. Models were then evaluated for face validity and performance (discrimination and calibration), and those considered of value were then externally validated in other available datasets.

A total of 503,923 participants were included, with size per data source ranging from 158,549 to 15,292. Overall, 90-day mortality, VTE, infection and readmission were seen in a range 0.20%-0.32%, 1.7%-3.0%, 7.1%-9.0%, 2.2%-4.8% respectively. Five-year revision surgery was observed in 1.5%-3.1% of participants. None of the models for VTE or infection had good performance.

We trained models for 90-day mortality, VTE, infection, readmission, and 5-year revision. Only 90-day mortality yielded AUROC > 0.70, other outcomes were not predictive. 90-day mortality had AUC of 0.78 and 0.68 in internal validation on Optum and THIN respectively, and the Optum model got 0.69, 0.86, 0.76, 0.72 AUC in external validation on THIN, Columbia, Stanford and MDCD.

During these 5-days we have developed and externally validated prediction tools for the identification of subjects at high risk of short-term mortality as well as developing models for readmission, venous thromboembolism and long-term revision. The primary finding of the research is high predictability of short-term mortality and the unpredictability of the other investigated outcomes. This suggests that decisions can be stratified based on varied risk of short-term mortality but that no such nuance can be applied to advice based on the concern of the other complications. A publication on this work has already been submitted to a high-impact journal and the work has been accepted for an oral presentation at the next conference of the International Society for Pharmacoepidemiology (ISPE)

In the upcoming period this use case will be further developed. We will execute the analytical pipeline on prediction problems defined by the upcoming study-a-thons. The study-a-thons are perfect mechanism to train new users of the tools and create valuable prediction models for patient care at the same time.

2.1.2 Utilising unstructured data

Electronic health record (EHR) databases are a rich source of data for building patient level prediction models. Currently, these models mainly use structured data (coded information and measurements) as features (2). However, many EHR databases also contain large amounts of unstructured, textual data (3). Natural language processing (NLP) to unlock these data has mainly been used for case identification. Previous studies have shown that case detection improves when textual data are combined with coded data (4). However, the value of this information to improve patient-level prediction models has largely been unexplored.

The aim of this EHDEN use case is to determine the added value of textual data in EHRs for improving patient-level prediction models. We will investigate a variety of methods to generate text-based features and determine whether predictive performance improves if these features are used in addition to the features based on coded information.

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Different feature sets will be generated and tested for their predictive value. As a baseline, bag-of-word approaches will be considered. Second, dictionary-based approaches will be used to identify relevant concepts (e.g., symptoms, conditions, procedures) in the texts. For concept recognition, deep-learning based language models will be explored (e.g., BERT (5), UMLFit (6)). Different automated feature extraction techniques (e.g., SAFE (7), AFEP (8)) will be applied to select the most informative features. Thirdly, topic modelling (latent Dirichlet allocation (9)) will be used to generate new features. Finally, several recently proposed methods for EHR-based phenotyping that do not require sample annotation (e.g., PheNorm (10)), will be investigated.

Contextual information in EHRs (e.g., negation, experiencer, temporal aspects, severity) will be detected and used to filter the textual data (11). Also, spelling correction algorithms will be applied (12). The impact of these pre-processing steps on predictive performance will be assessed.

Two important aspects that will be addressed are being multi-lingual and scalability. Since EHR data may stem from different countries, the investigated methods need to be able to cope with different languages (11). In this use case, several European languages will be considered. The Unified Medical Language System (UMLS) will be used as the main resource for non-English dictionaries. If a dictionary is not or only partially available in a non-English language of interest, we will apply automatic machine translation to generate the terms (13). With respect to language models, pre-trained models are publicly available in many languages and may be fine-tuned to the task at hand.

Also, it should be possible to apply the methods on a large scale, for many different outcomes and covariates. Therefore, methods will need to be scalable, in particular with respect to their requirements of annotated data sets for training. Scalability requires the use of unsupervised and semi-supervised methods as much as possible. Most of the proposed methods fall in these categories. In particular, we will investigate the use of pre-trained models and unlabelled data sets (5, 6). Also, zero-shot and few-shot learning techniques will be explored (14, 15).

The primary data source for method development and evaluation will be the Dutch Integrative Primary Care Information (IPCI) database, comprising general practitioner records and specialist letters of more than 2 million patients in the Netherlands. Most of the information in IPCI is in unstructured, textual format. Currently, only the coded information in IPCI has been mapped to the OMOP CDM. Additional data sources with textual data, in Dutch and other European languages, will be included when they become available in the project. Once the current patient-level prediction pipeline has been extended with a text-mining component, the potential value of textual information for patient-level prediction will be assessed for a wide range of outcomes and target cohorts.

2.1.3 Signal Detection

The signal detection use case is developed by WP1 and WP3 because of its prediction component. This is a proof-of-concept study evaluating EHDEN tools for post marketing drug safety surveillance (pharmacovigilance). Previously identified signals from the WHO global database of individual case safety reports will be studied as detailed below. New signals (up to a maximum of 3 per year) will further be explored for evaluation in subsequent years (2020-2022) during bespoke research activities in collaboration with partners in WP1, WP3 and WP3.

The overarching aim of this use case is to test existing tools (as developed by the OHDSI community) for population-level estimation and patient-level prediction, to expand their use and capabilities, and to develop new analytical tools where needed.

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The specific objectives of this use case are:

1. To analyse previously identified signals by Uppsala Monitoring Centre in mapped CPRD, namely:
 - a. the association between subcutaneous Denosumab use and the risk of vasculitis;
 - b. the association between Ceftriaxone use and the risk of liver injury in patients aged 75 years
2. To develop prediction tools for the risk of these adverse drug reactions amongst users of these same drugs;
3. To detect new safety signals in iterative analyses of VigiBase (in 2020-2022), and to repeat steps 1 to 2 to expand the knowledge regarding the association between drug-ADR combinations detected and evaluate the possibility to confirm/reject them through mapped data in EHDEN.

Multiple European databases standardised to the OMOP CDM will be used for analyses in this use case.

In a first clinical example, study participants will include 2 cohorts of target drugs users (denosumab, ceftriaxone), and 2 matched active comparator cohorts (alendronic acid and amoxicillin respectively). Propensity scores will be estimated with Lasso regression to minimise confounding. Cox regression will be used to calculate Hazard Ratios (HR) according to drug use. Each drug pair will be analysed separately. Self-controlled case series will be conducted with study participants with outcomes. These protocols have been approved by data access committees for one database so far (the Dutch IPCI primary care records database), and is currently under evaluation by the UK CPRD ISAC committee.

Similar analyses based on additional safety signals will be repeated in subsequent years. In these, new potential safety signals will be identified using the VigiTrace algorithm for further research in clinical data using the methods described above in a collaboration involving WP1 and WP3. As a second step, prediction algorithms will be developed to identify drug users at high risk of the potential safety events and validated externally in all available mapped datasets.

2.2. Risk Effect Estimation

The large amount of observational European healthcare data that will become available through EDHEN offers potential to estimate effects of medical products at large scale. Population-level risk effect estimation aims to assess the causal effect of treatments on the outcome, for example safety surveillance by product manufacturers and regulatory agencies, and evaluation of comparative (cost) effectiveness for payers and providers. The utilization of observational data for causality assessments has been criticized because of its lack of randomization. However, the development of advanced analytical methods including propensity score matching, and empirical calibration methods have shown the great potential of this type of data. For personalized medicine, causality assessments are critical to determine the optimal treatment for patients. This is of particular relevance for elderly patients and those with multiple co-morbidity: although they are amongst the most common users of drugs, they are seldom recruited in pivotal randomized controlled trials, leaving a gap in the knowledge of the effect of drugs in these patient group.

We have further intensified our collaboration with OHDSI's risk-effect estimation workgroup to extend the methods library which aims to support treatment choice. As described in more details below our work is focused on the extension of the methods library with risk stratified analysis of treatment effect. Furthermore, we will implement additional methods for propensity score matching, e.g. random forests, and will apply other study designs available from the OHDSI community.

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2.2.1 Risk Effect Estimation Study-a-thons

To further develop and execute the population-level risk effect estimation pipelines we will initiate multiple studies in WP3. At the study-a-thon at Oxford we also demonstrated the power of federated analyses using OMOP-mapped data and the available analytical pipeline in the risk effect estimation domain. As a proof-of-principle, we emulated a recently completed randomised controlled trial of unicompartmental vs total knee replacement, the Total or Partial Knee Arthroplasty Trial (TOPKAT), using routinely-collected data <https://trialsjournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1745-6215-14-292>

Five US and UK healthcare databases part of the OHDSI network were analysed. As with the target trial, post-operative complications (venous thromboembolism, infection, readmission, and mortality) were considered over 60 days following surgery and implant survival over five years following surgery. Clinical effectiveness was assessed using opioid use, as a proxy measure for persistent pain, from 91 to 365 days after surgery. Propensity score matched Cox proportional hazards models were fitted for each outcome. Hazard Ratios (HRs) were calibrated using negative and positive control outcomes to minimise residual confounding.

In total, 32,376 and 250,295 individuals who received unicompartmental and total knee replacement respectively were matched and included in the analysis. Unicompartmental knee replacement was consistently associated with a reduced risk of venous thromboembolism (calibrated HRs: 0.47 (0.31 - 0.73) to 0.76 (0.58 to 1.00)), although there was insufficient evidence to conclude there was a reduction in risk of infection, readmission, or mortality. Unicompartmental knee replacement was also associated with a reduced risk of opioid use (calibrated HRs: 0.72 (0.63 to 0.84) to 0.86 (0.74 to 1.01)), but an increased risk of revision (calibrated HRs: 1.48 (1.25 to 1.83) to 1.76 (1.42 to 2.32)).

Based on our results, we predict TOPKAT will find an increased risk of revision but improved patient reported outcomes for unicompartmental knee replacement. While the trial is not powered to assess complications, we find unicompartmental knee replacement to be a safer procedure with a reduced risk of venous thromboembolism. The results from this analysis were reported in the form of a podium presentation at the European League Against Rheumatism (EULAR) scientific conference last June, and highlighted in a [press release](#) instigated by EULAR that same week.

In addition, we developed and validated (both internally and externally) prediction algorithms for the identification of patients at risk of post-operative complications (venous thrombo-embolism, cardiovascular disease, prosthetic/surgical infection, and mortality). The results from this prediction were reported as an oral communication at the IOF-ESCEO conference in Paris last April.

We were able to design and execute this study within a week and have been able to submit a publication on the results in 1,5 months after the study-a-thon. Clearly, the execution time of a study is dependent on other factors such as well-established governance and ethical procedures, but the point here is to demonstrate the power of the analytical pipeline.

2.2.2 Improving Propensity Scores

In WP3, we are also working on methods research related to improving propensity score matching by conducting a series of simulations. We are estimating the performance of different machine learning algorithms in calculating the estimated propensity score compared to logistic regression. The proposed algorithms were tested in different scenarios of prevalence of exposure (from 1% to 50%), and in the presence of simple (linear, without interactions) vs complex (with interactions and non-linear terms) data structures. The machine learning algorithms tested were Bayesian Additive Regression Trees (BART), Random Forests, Support Vector Machines, and Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM). These experiments, all based on simulated data, will be replicated in OMOP-mapped datasets using clinical examples, in the context of

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propensity score methods for risk effect estimation. This research has the potential to create guidance for the use of machine learning methods for propensity score estimation in different scenarios combining different values of sample size, prevalence of exposure (from rare to common), and data structure including interactions and non-linear terms.

2.2.3. Heterogeneity of Treatment Effect

Heterogeneity of treatment effect (HTE) is the non-random explainable variability in the direction or magnitude of treatment effects for individuals within a population. Traditional approaches of HTE analysis, such as one-variable-at-a-time subgroup analyses suffer from multiplicity issues while they often fail to capture the multivariate nature of patient heterogeneity. It is widely recognized that average treatment effects found in randomized clinical trials may not always apply to all individual patients, giving rise to heterogeneity of treatment effects (HTE) that can often be quite substantial (16). Conventional subgroup analyses are incongruent with the goals of predictive HTE analyses. As such methods allow patients to differ on one measured variable at a time -while they may adequately detect relative effect modification- they fail to capture the multivariate nature of patient heterogeneity, i.e. a patient has an indefinite number of attributes causing them to belong in an indefinite number of subgroups (17). Prioritizing outcome risk as the subgrouping variable may resolve many of the issues arising from conventional analyses. Outcome risk is a summary score and -unlike individual variables that may or may not modify treatment effect- mathematically determines treatment effect (18).

For this use case we have developed an R package in EHDEN that provides insight into HTE using a risk-based approach (<https://github.com/mi-erasmusmc/RiskStratifiedEstimation>). As a proof-of-concept we applied this methodology in assessing HTE of ACE-inhibitors compared to Beta blockers with respect to cardiovascular disease events (CVD) and cough events in Truven MarketScan Commercial Claims and Encounters (CCA) database. Table 1 below describes the treatment, comparator, and outcome cohorts.

Table 1. Cohort definitions of the considered demonstration.

Cohort	Definition
<i>Treatment</i> (ACE inhibitors)	Hypertensive patients receiving drugs within the ACE inhibitor drug major class.
<i>Comparator</i> (Beta blockers)	Hypertensive patients receiving drugs within the Beta blocker drug major class.
<i>Outcome1</i> (CVD)	Total cardiovascular disease events (ischemic stroke, hemorrhagic stroke, heart failure, acute myocardial infarction or sudden death).
<i>Outcome 2</i> (Cough)	Cough events.

We applied the following methods:

- Personalized predictions of CVD risk were estimated using LASSO logistic regression on the combined treatment and comparator cohorts.
- Propensity scores were estimated using LASSO logistic regression within quartiles of predicted CVD risk.
- Covariates were balanced using inverse probability of treatment weights.
- Relative risks of CVD events were estimated using weighted Cox proportional hazards regression within quartiles of predicted CVD risk.

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- Absolute risk reduction in CVD risk was estimated using the difference of the weighted Kaplan-Meier estimators within quartiles of predicted CVD risk.
- Relative and absolute risk differences of cough events within quartiles of predicted CVD risk were made in the same way as above.

The results of the study showed that CVD hazard ratios are quite constant across quartiles of predicted CVD risk, leading to increasing absolute treatment benefits in favour of ACE inhibitors (Figure 1). There appears to be increased cough risk for patients receiving ACE inhibitors. However, absolute cough risk does not increase with CVD risk, encouraging the use of ACE inhibitors for high CVD risk patients.

Figure 1. Relative and absolute treatment effects within risk strata

The results of our proof-of-concept study has demonstrated the value of the implemented heterogeneity of treatment effect method. We therefore continue our work by adding HTE to OHDSI’s LEGEND study (for more information see <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=so5gsCl7CU4>). Moreover, we will fully incorporate this new analytical tool in the EHDEN ecosystem, e.g., enable network study execution and develop dashboards for HTE analysis.

2.3 Disease Trajectories

Electronic health records (EHR), especially when collected over a long period, are a valuable resource for investigating disease trajectories – how certain health events follow each other. By extending our knowledge about how diseases develop in time, how diagnoses follow each other, and what are the main pathways from particular health-related event to another, we could utilize this information for better disease prediction, prevention, treatment selection, and optimizing internal healthcare processes. Disease trajectories are not necessarily limited to diseases/diagnoses only, they may also contain healthcare services and their costs, used medications, etc.

Disease trajectory analyses can be largely divided into two groups: trajectories that lead to a certain event (usually a disease), and trajectories that begin with certain health event. The former of them can be used in the context of prediction because they try to identify, what are the pathways that lead to the investigated event – what preceding events do they contain, what is the distance in time, etc. This increases our

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understanding of the root causes and risk factors of the disease. For instance, many common diseases like type 2 diabetes and cardiovascular diseases are preceded by lifestyle-related events like being diagnosed as obese or being an active smoker. But there might be also many other health-related events that tend to occur before the disease. By taking into account all these events we can test whether our patient is on any of these tracks to develop these diseases. What is more, if some events in the track could be avoided by applying lifestyle changes (e.g. being physically more active), we could move patient off from this track and thereby prevent the manifestation of the disease.

An alternative method is to investigate what happens to the patients after a certain event/diagnose. This is useful when studying the patient flow through the medical system - what healthcare services were provided for him/her, in which order, in which time period. This would allow analysing the outcomes of the treatment - possibly depending on the pathways (different therapies) that the patients went through. It also allows detecting bottlenecks and inefficiencies in the processes.

By combining both methods, one could make longer predictions about the general population - what diagnoses are likely to pop up during next year, what is the estimated costs for their treatments, etc.

Two diagnosis groups are in the initial interests in EHDEN project - type 2 diabetes and cardiovascular diseases. Both are non-communicable diseases, highly prevalent in the European population, and besides genetic risk factors, unhealthy lifestyle plays an important role when developing these diseases. By investigating disease trajectories of these diseases, we can focus on both sides of the diagnosis - preceding events (for prevention) and the events that follow the diagnosis (for predicting next events and estimate the costs for healthcare).

For successful detection of disease trajectories, a large observational health dataset is needed. Previous studies have focused on investigating disease pairs within the data and it is tested for each pair whether their order is significant. The results are usually represented as graphs where nodes denote the events and directional links between them represent the order.

Another classical approach to investigate event sequences is to utilize Hidden Markov Model (HMM). The concept of HMM is that there is a certain number of hidden states in the model and when moving between the states, events (diseases, healthcare services, etc.) are emitted. HMM detects these states and identifies the links between states. Therefore, having only one input parameter (number of states), HMM generalizes the whole data to certain states and trajectories between them.

The problem is that in the context where there might be thousands of types of health events, it is difficult to interpret these states, and, therefore, giving the clinical meaning for these states and links between them is a challenging task that we will try to tackle in this use case.

As a first step, we focus on condition occurrences of the OMOP common data model as health events. We try to identify what are the preceding and following events for getting type 2 diabetes and coronary heart disease. To achieve that, we utilize HMM model to detect hidden states that lead to these diseases and try to give a clinical meaning to them. The results of this work will be delivered in D3.6.

3. CONCLUSION

The WP3 team has selected a large list of use cases in the personalized medicine domain that will further drive the development of the EHDEN ecosystem. We have also been able to demonstrate the power of the approach in several study-a-thons. These study-a-thons enable multiple stakeholders to experience the improvement in speeds of study execution without negatively impacting the quality of the results. Clearly, the best way to convince stakeholders that the standardisation to the OMOP-CDM is worth the effort, is by answering the clinical questions they have on the spot. The demonstration of the tools and pipelines is a very

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powerful mechanism to expand the community. Therefore, we will be organizing more of these exciting meetings across Europe to collaboratively generate reliable evidence.

In the upcoming period WP3 will work on the extension of the analytical pipelines and their incorporation in the tools for federated study execution as described in this deliverable. Together with WP1 and WP2 we will execute the use cases to data sources that are already mapped to the OMOP-CDM. Finally, WP3 will be developing training material for the EHDEN Academy to enable all stakeholders to leverage the important work done in this domain.

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